

Alternative to the Binomial Series or Binomial Theorem

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents an alternative to the existing binomial series or binomial theorem. This alternative binomial theorem uses the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series for constructing the new binomial series. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial coefficient

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-13]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the combinatorial geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, an alternative to the existing binomial series or binomial theorem is constituted for further research and development.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-13] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Here, $V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers .

$V_n^r = V_r^n, (n, r > 0$ and $n, r \in N)$ is an important binomial identity.

$V_n^0 = V_0^n$ for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

3. Alternative to Binomial Series

The existing binomial series or binomial theorem is given below:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} x^{n-i} y^i = x^n + \binom{n}{1} x^{n-1} y + \binom{n}{2} x^{n-2} y^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{k} x^{n-k} y^k + \dots + y^n = (x + y)^n.$$

If $x = y = 1$, then $\sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} = \binom{n}{0} + \binom{n}{1} + \binom{n}{2} + \dots + \binom{n}{k} + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} + \binom{n}{n} = 2^n$.

The alternative to the above binomial theorem or binomial series is given below:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^n x^{n-i} y^i = x^n + V_1^n x^{n-1} y + V_2^n x^{n-1} y + \dots + V_k^n x^{n-k} y^k + \dots + V_n^n y^n, (V_0^n = 1).$$

If $x = y = 1$, then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^n = V_0^n + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n + \dots + V_k^n + \dots + V_{n-1}^n + V_n^n = V_n^{n+1}$.

Here, $V_0^n = 1$; $V_1^n = (n + 1)$; $V_2^n = \frac{(n + 1)(n + 2)}{2!}$; $V_k^n = \frac{(n + 1)(n + 2) \dots (n + k)}{n!}$, and so on.

4. Conclusion

In this article, an alternative to the existing binomial series or binomial theorem was constituted using the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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